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Dynamic Speed Limits System: Case Study in Helmond

Iñaki Dacasa^{1*}, Christian López¹, Javier Vázquez¹, Raúl Urbano¹, René Spaan², Pablo Dafonte¹

1. CTAG – Automotive Technology Centre of Galicia, Polígono Industrial "A GRANXA", Calle "A", 249-250
Porriño 36475 (Pontevedra). Spain.

2. Gemeente Helmond, PO Box 950, 5700 AZ Helmond, Netherlands

inaki.dacasa@ctag.com

Abstract

Urbanization and continuing car dependence lead to inevitable traffic congestion, emissions and mobility-safety problems for transport policymakers and urban planners. With most EU-citizens (over 70%) living in urban areas of which most in small and medium-sized cities, they should be ground target to promote the accomplishments and innovations and position them as excellent living labs for innovation. Considerable advances have been made in designing and implementing traffic control and regulations preparing the proper transition to the new and demanding agenda of European small and medium-sized cities regarding speed adaptation and ultimately decarbonization. This study presents a solution capable of being integrated into the traffic management value-chain, offering a bridge between Intelligent Speed Assistance systems and the physical and digital infrastructure of cities. This solution has been tested in the city of Helmond to demonstrate the clear role of medium-sized cities in the adoption of innovations to accomplish future mobility challenges.

Keywords: PILOT PROJECTS AND DEMONSTRATIONS, USER BEHAVIOUR AND ACCEPTANCE, DYNAMIC SPEED LIMITS, MEDIUM-SIZE CITIES, INTELLIGENT SPEED ASSISTANCE.

Introduction

With most EU-citizens (over 70 %) living in urban areas of which most in small and medium-sized cities (SMCs) (Demazière, 2017), Polis Network strongly believe in the potential of the SMCs as ideal grounds to promote the accomplishments and innovations of small and medium-sized cities and position them as excellent living labs for innovation. The city of Helmond (Netherlands) was one of the first signatories of the SMCs Ambassadors Initiative (POLIS, 2019).

Urbanization and continuing car dependence lead to inevitable traffic congestion, emissions, and mobility safety problems (beesmarcity, 2018) for transport policymakers and urban planners. According to the European Joint Research Centre, "the cost of road congestion in Europe is equivalent to an estimated 1% of GDP, and its mitigation is the main priority of most infrastructure, traffic management and road charging measures (Panayotis Christidis, 2012).

Considerable advances have been made in designing and implementing traffic control and regulation preparing the proper transition to the new and demanding agenda of European small and medium-sized regarding speed adaptation and ultimately decarbonization (Fuso Nerini F, 2019).

Advanced forms of traffic signalling are often self-optimizing and self-organizing catering for different scenarios in large urban and metropolitan areas where there is a need to control traffic and give priority to public transport (Roozemon, 1998). From a safety perspective, improving signal timing can reduce speed dispersion, reduce the occurrence of rear-end collisions, prevent accidents resulting through red-light violations, and provide added protection to pedestrians and cyclists (Taylor, 1997).

As a component of Active Traffic Management (ATM), Dynamic Speed Limit (DSL) systems aims to improve traffic safety through reductions in mean speeds and in speed variations within and across lanes, and between upstream and downstream flows. Apart from affecting traffic safety, DSLs could also have effects on smoother traffic flow, congestion, and travel times, as well as on vehicle emissions and road noise. Variable Speed Limits (VSL) are often used as a synonym for DSLs (Daniels, 2017). DSL or VSL uses infrastructure-based technologies such as Variable Message Signs (VMS) are often used to inform drivers of crashes, adverse road conditions such as congestion, road works, weather conditions, or other factors requiring an increase in awareness and a reduction in speed. These signs are often automated or semi-automated in conjunction with a traffic management and control strategy and can provide timely information as and when it is needed (Transportation Research Board, 1998).

According to Transportation Research Board (1998), compliance with any speed limit regulation requires that it represents a reasonable constraint on behaviour. For compliance with speed limits to be high, most of the drivers must perceive them to be legitimate and comply with them voluntarily. Otherwise, they are likely to be disregarded.

Both traffic operators and vehicle manufacturers have had a strong interest in the development of information and communication technologies over the years, so called Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) (European Parliament, 2009), and systems and technologies supporting ITS have been developed and deployed all over the world. This can be achieved by introducing new methods using connected vehicles or extending existing methods to include them. Connected vehicles can be used in combination with stationary detectors or as a standalone source of information. The main benefit of using connected vehicles for traffic state estimations is the possibility to get information at arbitrary locations, which is not possible with the stationary detectors (Grumert, 2018); as well as planning and applying pollution reduction regulations due to their capability of generating an automated ecosystem where every vehicle is aware of what is going on around it (Ku D., 2020).

One of the most direct means of reducing vehicle speed and crash risk is through the introduction of speed limiting and Intelligent Speed Adaptation (ISA) devices. Under Article 6 of Regulation (EU) (2019/2144) motor vehicles of categories M and N must be equipped with certain advanced vehicle systems, including ISA. ISA systems can make use of various input methods, such as camera observation, map data and machine learning (COMMISSION DELEGATED REGULATION (EU) 2021/1958).

Several research projects such as the H2020 project ReVeAL (Sadler, 2021) have also contributed to help medium-sized cities to adopt or test technological solutions such as geofencing or ADAS-based solutions. The project Efficient Traffic Control with Variable Speed Limits: Bridging the gap between Theory and Practical Implementation (2019) delivered a logic-based speed limit control algorithm for Variable Speed Limits to reduce traffic congestion at bottlenecks.

Studies have shown how connected vehicles can be used as part of a VSL system (Yang, 2014). They use connected vehicles to calculate a speed limit with the objective to smooth the vehicle trajectories in stop and go traffic. The authors show that by making use of connected vehicles, the environmental impacts can be reduced without decreasing traffic efficiency. Moreover, the emerging connected car industry offers huge opportunities in creating and developing ICT-based technologies for the automotive sector, as well as new business models beyond the traditional vehicle manufacturing (Ana Paul, 2018). On 8 October 2020, the European Commission and the Transport Area of the Florence School of Regulation organised an executive seminar with applied experts, researchers, and stakeholders on speed management in European road safety policy. The participants agreed on the importance of data and its collection methods as this is the key support tool for developing evidence-based road safety policies, such as KPIs; nothing that we increasingly have the potential to gather data to radically transform crash investigation involving K/SI; to make more use of DSLs (linked to future developments of dynamic ISA) and for better enforcement more generally and for driver support (European Commission, 2020).

Description of the value proposition of CELESTE as a DSL compliance Solution

CELESTE is a collaborative project, part of the portfolio of activities of the Knowledge and Innovation Community of the EIT Urban Mobility (Project CELESTE). The CELESTE Platform aims at modifying the current structure of traffic control in the cities and transform it into an active planification capable of reacting and adapting to the traffic situations in real-time with help of a dynamic speed limit, offering more safety roads and increasing the traffic fluidity. CELESTE Platform encapsulates a connection with the Road Information Platforms of the cities, a Human-Machine Interface, a Speed Limit Calculator Algorithm, and a connection with a CELESTE Mobile App.

While most of the data will be directly provided in an online and programmatic manner through the Road Information Platforms, TMCs or road operators also have the possibility to insert data when specific situations require so. The solution embraces, on one hand the main source of information from the traffic environment and, on the other hand, particular data when specific situations, like unexpected events or bad weather conditions require it. For example, these dynamic speed solutions can be applied periodically during certain periods of time in specific areas, such as schools, theatres, and commercial centres; applied manually where non periodically events take place like stadiums, congress centres and events centres or when unforeseen situations appear in roads or highways, increasing citizens safety.

Design of the demonstration architecture

The architecture designed outlines a Software as a Service (SaaS) where all the data needed is available, in real time, to Traffic Management Centres (TMCs), to the Celeste Mobile App or to adapted/connected vehicles. The architecture solution seeks to integrate both static as well as dynamic data from the city with the dynamic speed calculator algorithm offering in real time the recommended speed to the users.

Figure 1 - Architecture

CELESTE mobile APP

The main goal of CELESTE is to make this Dynamic Speed Adaptation available to everyone, for this, an app has been created. CELESTE Mobile App was developed by the Automotive Technology Centre of Galicia (CTAG), has been tested in CTAG’s test tracks, and was used during CELESTE Demonstrations in Helmond.

The main screen of the application is similar to a typical navigation screen, displaying the current limit speed of the road in the top left corner.

Figure 2 - CELESTE App (Main Screen). Source: CTAG.

Once the user enters the area that contains a dynamic recommended speed limit, the application makes an alerting sound and displays an information panel at the top left of the screen that shows the new recommended speed limit and the reason of this speed change. The panel remains on the screen while the user stays in the event area.

Figure 3 - CELESTE App (Event area). Source: CTAG. CELESTE Platform performance in real scenarios

City Introduction

The city of Helmond is a medium-sized city with 92.000 inhabitants located in the Brainport region in the South of the Netherlands (Figure 4). Together with its Industrial and Research Partners and Academia in this region, the city is offering a Smart Mobility Living Lab, with the Automotive Campus Helmond

as a physical hotspot for smart mobility innovations. The Automotive Campus serves as a home base for project teams, that are operating smart mobility pilots in Helmond. The Automotive Campus is also home to the national traffic management centre for the south of the Netherlands. Since the early 2000s the city of Helmond is heavily involved in European Smart Mobility projects.

Figure 4 – Brainport region and provincial N270 that goes through Helmond

Due to the number of inhabitants and roads, Helmond does not have its own TMC, but the traffic in the city is guided by more than 55 intelligent traffic controllers (iVRI) which are supervised daily by the city of Helmond. Hence, it is very interesting to participate in developing a solution to apply dynamic speeds in a medium sized city where the opportunities lie to easily scale it up to larger surrounding cities and counteract traffic congestion.

With 464 per 1,000 inhabitants, car ownership in Helmond is above average compared to other cities in the Netherlands (ValueCare, 2022). This number also continues to grow every year, which means that traffic congestion, accidents and dangerous situations also continue to increase. In the traffic vision for 2020-2040, Helmond expects a growth of more than 10% on current traffic movements of cars, especially on the provincial road that goes right through the core of the city (Helmond, 2020). In addition, the city of Helmond has areas where many unsafe traffic situations occur daily, for example around schools and shopping areas where it is common to cross the road frequently.

Helmond and Data

Existing traffic information and navigation services are using traffic data supplied by various sources. One gateway for this traffic information and other related products is the Dutch National Data Bank for Traffic Data (NDW, 2021). On the other hand, road operators must publish traffic decisions, including, for example, a temporary road closure (Wegbeheerders, n.d.). This information is all retrieved by service providers and then distributed to the users (Overheid, 2022). Thereby, this is where CELESTE comes in aggregating all that data and presenting a visual web-based module allowing its integration even if there is no TMC.

Setting-up the living lab

A living lab was defined with a route of 6,6 km around the Automotive Campus and consist of four specific scenarios: Hoofdstraat, Beatrixlaan, Julianalaan and Dorpsstraat. The Figure 5 shows the geographical location of this living lab in the city of Helmond.

Figure 5 – Geographical location of the living lab near the Automotive Campus

1. Hoofdstraat – ‘t Hout

Hoofdstraat is characterized by a lot of activity during different times at a day. It is surrounded by shops, a supermarket, a railway crossing, a school, a church, and a lot of parking spaces. In a radius of just 500 meters, while the speed limit is 50 km/h, it gives a feeling of unsafety to the citizens, especially during opening times of the shops and supermarket and during start and end of school since people drive and/or park their cars, ride their bicycles, or walk to school.

2. Beatrixlaan – city centre

Beatrixlaan is a restricted 30 km/h area and often used as a shortcut road. It encompasses three specific locations, where 30km/h feels too fast from a safety viewpoint: A busy crossing with many cyclists (Prins Hendriklaan towards Beatrixlaan), a right turn with a limited view on upcoming traffic and a priority road with a limited view around the corner.

3. Julianalaan – city centre Julianalaan is a 50km/h area with a school in the neighbourhood characterized by a lot of activity during different times at a day, it attracts many cyclists that in combination with a regular traffic leads to a feeling of unsafety.

4. Dorpsstraat – Stiphout

The situation in the Dorpsstraat is very similar to the Hoofdstraat. It is a 50km/h area with a road often crossed by pedestrians, surrounded by shops, a supermarket, a school, and a church. The default speed limit gives a feeling of unsafety to the citizens, especially during opening times of the shops and supermarket and during start and end hours of the school.

The main objective of the city of Helmond, in the areas and roads previously mentioned, is to achieve a safe environment by applying dynamic speed limits, reducing the speed limit in the areas during busy hours and unsafe specific locations (described in Beatrixlaan) while still maintaining the default speed limit during quiet hours and safe locations.

Launching the demonstration

CELESTE Platform was tested in a living lab designed to solve the problematics approached in the previous section. The demonstration took place on December 2nd, 2021, and was performed in a Skoda Enyaq 2021 (100% electric) arranged by SKODA while using the CELESTE Mobile App.

For this demonstration, the road operator specified busy hours and unsafe factors such as, dense traffic,

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school, marketplace areas and general hazards in the CELESTE platform. The platform programmatically calculated and advised a new speed limit for the road and area, such speed if accepted by the road operator is sent to the CELESTE Mobile App and the connected vehicles driving in the area. The information specified by the road operator gave a total of 7 different events.

Table 1 - Helmond demonstration events. Own elaboration.

Scenario	Type of Event	Text	Start Coordinates	End Coordinates
Hoofdstraat	Event Area	Shopping area	51.467058, 5.634406	51.46626, 5.634615
Hoofdstraat	School Area	School area	51.467812, 5.634607	51.467236, 5.634382
Beatrixlaan	Event Area	Sharp curve	51.480542, 5.647225	51.480996, 5.647879
Beatrixlaan	Event Area	Crossing without priority	51.480873, 5.649560	51.480626, 5.650933
Julianalaan	School Area	School area	51.485251, 5.650259	51.484837, 5.648849
Dorpsstraat	Event Area	Supermarket area	51.484511, 5.622477	51.486034, 5.619650
Dorpsstraat	School Area	School area	51.486668, 5.617607	51.487366, 5.615377

The information about the events was received and displayed in the CELESTE App, while the driving was done manually, this allowed to the driver to notice the information of the events dynamically. The images below outline the process, using as example the “School area” event created in Julianalaan (**¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**):

A vehicle is moving down a street under regular conditions, there is no alert on the app nor dangerous situation on the road (Figure 7).

Once the driver enters an area or road containing an event, the app shows the information of the new speed limit and the text associated to it, so the driver is able to adapt the speed accordingly (**¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**).

After the area or road of the event, the App erases the panel, and the driver returns to increase the speed to reach the default limit of the road (Figure 9).

Figure 6 - Julianalaan Event

Figure 7 - Driving under regular

Figure 9 - Driving in an event area

Figure 8 - Driving under regular conditions

Conclusions

The demonstration conducted in the living lab designed in the city of Helmond demonstrates how a medium-sized city can be ready to deploy a dynamic speed limits strategy using CELESTE even without having a proper TMC. During the preparation stage, up to 7 events were created by the road operator through the REST API based on the problematics experienced in the selected locations. These events were created by inserting several parameters to the CELESTE Platform that determine the preferable speed limit of a certain area of the road. CELESTE App was installed in 2 different Android devices, and both worked correctly without any defect during the demonstration. Throughout the execution, 3 rounds were performed around the predefined route, reaching a 100% success of the events appearing in the right place (starting point of the event) at the right time in the CELESTE Mobile App.

Through this project demonstration, it was possible to verify how the proposed solution represents an anticipated answer to the upcoming regulation at a European level in terms of decarbonization and Intelligent Speed Advisory systems, as well as its feasible integration with the urban physical and digital infrastructure.

Based on the challenges explained in the areas selected for the demonstration, the city of Helmond believes that the CELESTE Platform can be a great asset to the future developments of a dynamic Intelligent Speed Adaptation (ISA). It can definitely help to a great extent to solve the challenges mentioned above, as a part of the traffic management strategy in medium-sized cities. Nevertheless, there are some hurdles that may appear when trying to scale the CELESTE Platform and make it available in other cities. The main identified issue may occur if cities do not have real-time information about their traffic and roads. To mitigate this issue, CELESTE Platform can receive and handle information from commercial navigation applications; also, events and traffic information could be manually created. Other detected issue is that the infrastructure needs to allow the users to always receive events on time, for that it is necessary to have internet coverage. Even though this is not a common problem in European cities, there could be places where this issue may appear.

Based on the results achieved within this demonstration, future works might include adding voice messages on the CELESTE Mobile App (to avoid distractions) as well as offering a summary of their driving statistics to raise awareness of the importance of respecting speed limits. In other terms, the standardization of communication protocols and messages is one of the next milestones in the roadmap, resorting to DATEX II to identify event codes (OpenStreetMap, 2014), location references and VMS publications. Thereby, this step enables three goals: a simplified and more efficient data exchange between CELESTE and TMCs, a proper integration within the physical city infrastructure (VMS) and the easiest data distribution to third parties responsible of navigation services for road-users.

Cities are the powerhouse of the modern economy and home to millions of people. Their inhabitants are increasingly facing challenges such as congestion, poor air quality and excessive noise. Therefore, experiments such as the one presented in this paper needs to be undertaken to test and evaluate measures and solutions to contribute to create liveable urban spaces.

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